

OpenDwarfs 2025: Modernizing the OpenDwarfs Benchmark Suite for Heterogeneous Computing

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Abstract. As the era of heterogeneous computing evolves, benchmarking tools are vital for measuring performance across diverse architectures. We present OpenDwarfs 2025, a reengineered and modernized version of the OpenDwarfs benchmark suite, originally developed to evaluate the performance of heterogeneous systems using OpenCL. Our comprehensive reengineering process involved addressing compatibility issues with modern compilers, resolving bugs, and enhancing usability to align the suite with the latest hardware advancements. Key updates include improved scalability, standardized configurations, and enriched documentation, making the suite more accessible to the research community. Experimental results highlight the enhanced performance and portability of OpenDwarfs 2025 across diverse platforms, offering valuable insights into the evaluation of parallel computing systems amidst rapidly advancing architectures.

Keywords: Heterogeneous computing · benchmark suite optimization · parallel computing performance · OpenCL benchmarks · software reengineering.

1 Introduction

Heterogeneous computing—combining multicore CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, and specialized accelerators—has become essential for meeting the performance demands of modern applications in AI, data science, and high-performance computing. Benchmark suites are vital for characterizing these diverse platforms, revealing each architecture’s strengths and limitations under real-world workloads.

The OpenDwarfs suite, originally built around the “13 Dwarfs of Berkeley” [2] and implemented in OpenCL, has served as a hardware-agnostic tool for evaluating parallel systems. This suite was first introduced by Feng *et al.* in [8], and its development continued in a second publication by Krommydas *et al.* [11]. However, eight years of limited maintenance have left its benchmarks outdated and cumbersome to build, configure, and run on today’s compilers and devices. Source-level issues, inconsistent configurations, sparse documentation, and lack

of automated input generators have hindered its utility for researchers and practitioners alike.

Our work, OpenDwarfs 2025, delivers a comprehensive modernization: All kernels now target OpenCL 1.1 by default, build and execution scripts are unified, and three standardized input-size categories (Test, Train, Reference) ensure reproducible workloads. New generators automate the creation of valid inputs for graph, matrix, and bioinformatics benchmarks, while enriched documentation guides users through compilation, device selection, and result collection. Extensive experiments on a heterogeneous cluster (128-core CPUs, multiple NVIDIA and AMD GPUs) validate improved portability, scalability and performance, with detailed speedup and scalability analyses highlighting both GPU advantages and areas for future optimization.

This paper presents several significant advancements in modernizing the OpenDwarfs benchmark suite, addressing critical gaps in compatibility, usability, and performance evaluation for heterogeneous computing systems. The primary contributions of this work are as follows:

- **Comprehensive Modernization:** Refactoring the OpenDwarfs suite to ensure compatibility with modern compilers, including GCC/G++ version 11.0, and hardware platforms such as GPUs and multicore CPUs. This ensures that the suite remains relevant in today’s rapidly evolving computational landscape.
- **Enhanced Usability:** Introducing standardized configurations and enriched documentation to simplify the setup, execution, and analysis of benchmarks. These improvements make OpenDwarfs 2025 more accessible to the research community, particularly for those unfamiliar with heterogeneous systems.
- **Expanded Functionality:** Adding new features such as input file generators and configurable parameters, which allow users to customize benchmarks for diverse workloads, including dynamic programming, linear algebra, and graph-based algorithms.
- **Systematic Performance Evaluation:** Conducting extensive experiments across heterogeneous architectures, including GPUs and CPUs, to analyze execution times, scalability, and speedup. These evaluations provide valuable insights into the strengths and limitations of each platform.

In summary, OpenDwarfs 2025 revives and extends the original suite, providing a robust and user-friendly framework for benchmarking next-generation heterogeneous systems. These contributions collectively ensure that OpenDwarfs 2025 serves as a strong and versatile tool for evaluating heterogeneous systems, aligning it with the needs of the high-performance computing community. The new OpenDwarfs 2025 benchmark suite is available at the following link: <https://github.com/uva-trasgo/OpenDwarfs2025>.

2 Structure of the Suite

The OpenDwarfs suite is a tool designed to evaluate the performance of heterogeneous systems using OpenCL. It is composed of a set of benchmarks based on

the “13 Dwarfs of Berkeley” [2], computational patterns that encapsulate fundamental operations of parallel algorithms. These benchmarks assess various types of workloads that can be executed on CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs, and other platforms. The suite is designed to be hardware-agnostic, allowing for performance comparisons across various architectures.

OpenDwarfs adheres to the philosophy of providing a test suite that encompasses the broadest possible diversity of computational patterns, enabling the evaluation of different aspects of performance across heterogeneous platforms. The benchmarks were selected to represent a range of parallel applications, covering areas such as dense and sparse linear algebra, spectral transformations, and dynamic methods, among others. Each benchmark was either developed from scratch using OpenCL or ported to OpenCL, with the aim of ensuring compatibility with a wide range of devices, from traditional processors to specialized hardware.

The OpenDwarfs suite contains benchmarks that represent algorithms and methods used in various scientific disciplines and applications. The suite covers 13 different categories, such as dense and sparse linear algebra, spectral methods, and dynamic programming, each represented by at least one benchmark. The suite also allows users to execute and analyze the results of these benchmarks under different hardware and software configurations. Below is a brief description of the benchmark included in the suite:

- **BFS (Breadth-First Search)**: Implements the breadth-first search algorithm, used in graph problems. Evaluates performance in traversing large graphs and calculating node costs from a root node [9].
- **BWA HMM (Baum-Welch Algorithm)**: Belongs to the category of graphical models and is based on the Baum-Welch algorithm, used for training hidden Markov models. Evaluates the ability to adjust parameters in large graphical models.
- **CFD (Computational Fluid Dynamics)**: Simulates computational fluid dynamics problems. This benchmark measures performance in operations involving partial differential equations used to model fluid flow [6].
- **CRC (Cyclic Redundancy Check)**: Computes CRC checksums, commonly used for error-detection in digital networks [7].
- **FFT (Fast Fourier Transform)**: Implements the fast Fourier transform, converting signals from the time domain to the frequency domain. This benchmark is essential for measuring performance in signal processing applications [5].
- **GEM (Generalized Matrix Operations)**: Conducts generalized matrix computations, such as matrix multiplication and transposition.
- **KMEANS**: A clustering algorithm that divides a set of points into groups based on their proximity. This benchmark is used in machine learning and data mining, evaluating clustering efficiency [12].
- **LUD (LU Decomposition)**: Performs the LU decomposition of matrices, a method widely used in solving systems of linear equations [3].

- **N-QUEENS**: Solves the N-Queens puzzle by finding all possible arrangements of N queens on an N×N chessboard such that no two queens threaten each other.
- **NW (Needleman-Wunsch)**: Implements the DNA sequence alignment algorithm. It is an example of dynamic programming and is used in bioinformatics to find the optimal alignment between two nucleotide sequences.
- **SPMV (Sparse Matrix-Vector Multiplication)**: Computes the multiplication of a sparse matrix and a vector.
- **SRAD (Speckle Reducing Anisotropic Diffusion)**: Applies a diffusion algorithm for image denoising, particularly for ultrasound images [13].
- **SWAT (Smith-Waterman Alignment Tool)**: Conducts local sequence alignment using the Smith-Waterman algorithm.
- **TDM (Tridiagonal Matrix Solver)**: Solves tridiagonal systems of linear equations using specialized algorithms.

Each benchmark is designed to evaluate a specific aspect of hardware performance, whether in terms of integer or floating-point computation, memory access, or parallelism. Running these benchmarks on different devices enables a comparative evaluation of the computational capabilities of such systems.

2.1 Compilation Prerequisites and Process

To compile and execute the OpenDwarfs benchmarks, several prerequisites must be met. These include installing a compiler compatible with OpenCL, such as GCC/G++ version 11.0 or later, and the necessary libraries to compile programs written in OpenCL. OpenDwarfs is designed to run on GNU/Linux systems, requiring the installation of tools such as `autoconf`, `automake`, `libtool`, and `make`. These packages facilitate the creation of automated build scripts and proper dependency management during the compilation process. Another crucial requirement is the installation of an OpenCL version compatible with the devices where the benchmarks will be executed. Although the suite was developed using OpenCL 1.0, newer versions of the standard can also be used. For easier configuration, tools like `clinfo`, which provides information about the OpenCL-compatible devices present in the system, are recommended.

The compilation process of the suite is divided into several steps to ensure that the benchmarks are correctly configured and generated on the machine where they will be executed. The main steps are as follows:

1. Run the `autogen.sh` script from the root directory of the repository. This script automatically generates header files and other necessary files for compilation.
2. Navigate to the `build` directory in the repository and execute the `configure` script. This script generates the `Makefiles` needed to compile the benchmarks.
3. Finally, run the `make` command to compile the selected benchmarks. During this step, executable files for each benchmark are generated along with the OpenCL kernels required for execution.

In some cases, additional options may need to be specified when running the `configure` script, such as selecting specific benchmarks or defining the path to the OpenCL SDK. This allows for adjustments to the compilation process according to the system's characteristics, where the benchmarks will be run.

2.2 Compatibility, Flexibility and Limitations

A key feature of the original OpenDwarfs is its flexibility. The suite is intended to be executed on a wide range of devices, including conventional processors, graphics cards, and specialized hardware such as FPGAs. Additionally, the suite allows users to adjust certain benchmark parameters, such as matrix sizes, the number of iterations, or the type of input used. This facilitates the customization of tests and the adaptation of the suite to different experimental scenarios.

In addition to its flexibility, the new OpenDwarfs 2025 provides a consistent user interface through command-line scripts. Users can compile, execute, and obtain benchmark results using a series of straightforward commands without needing to modify the source code.

Despite its many advantages, OpenDwarfs also has certain limitations. Some benchmarks require specific configurations that may not be available on all systems, making direct comparisons between different platforms complicated. Additionally, using OpenCL as the sole programming standard limits access to devices that are not compatible with this standard.

Another challenge of the original version is the need for manual adjustments to certain benchmarks to ensure they function correctly on newer hardware. This is because some benchmarks were developed several years ago and have not been updated to leverage the improvements in the latest versions of OpenCL.

3 Suite Reengineering Process

The reengineering process of the OpenDwarfs suite was carried out to address the various defects that hindered or prevented its use. The primary goal of this effort was to ensure that each benchmark provided correct and consistent outputs, enhancing the user experience and enabling precise comparisons between different platforms. One of the first issues addressed was the lack of uniformity in the OpenCL versions used. Many benchmarks generated warnings during compilation due to deprecated APIs or functions from older versions of OpenCL. The original developers had not updated the code to accommodate newer versions of the standard, resulting in compilation inconsistencies. To solve this, OpenCL 1.1 was set as the default version for all benchmarks in the suite by adding the macro `CL_TARGET_OPENCL_VERSION` with the value 110 in the necessary files. This change was implemented globally to prevent errors related to incorrect versions. Additionally, extensive compilation and execution tests were conducted for each modified benchmark. These tests ensured that changes to one benchmark did not negatively affect the others and that the suite could be reliably used across diverse platforms. The reengineering process of the OpenDwarfs

suite addressed multiple defects affecting benchmark execution. Each benchmark was thoroughly tested on heterogeneous platforms to ensure compatibility and functionality in modern environments. The changes not only restored the suite’s utility but also improved its usability.

The reengineering process for OpenDwarfs not only focused on fixing defects in the benchmarks but also on improving the overall usability of the suite. We have extensively worked to facilitate the execution of benchmarks and ensure that the system is more accessible for users while enabling more systematic experimental evaluations. Different input sets were established for experiments, inspired by those defined by SPEC CPU [1]. Three categories of input sets were implemented:

- **Test Input Set:** Designed for quick tests with an execution time of approximately one second. Its goal is to ensure that the benchmarks are correctly installed and functioning under minimal workloads.
- **Train Input Set:** Simulates moderate workloads, with executions lasting approximately 30 seconds. It is used to emulate more demanding working conditions.
- **Reference Input Set:** Designed to simulate realistic and heavy workloads, with execution times of around one minute. The results obtained are used to compare benchmark performance across different hardware platforms.

The estimated execution times were obtained using timers included in the benchmarks by the original developers. The aim was to observe the behavior of the benchmarks on various OpenCL platforms, with a particular focus on comparing the performance of CPUs and GPUs. Intuitively, GPUs should provide significant speedups compared to CPUs for specific benchmarks, such as CSR, GEM, and LUD, due to their ability to perform many mathematical computations in parallel.

One of the main changes to improve usability was standardizing the command-line invocations for the different benchmarks. This change reduced confusion when using the benchmarks, offering a more consistent interface for their execution. The original implementation for selecting OpenCL platforms and devices was reviewed and improved. Users can now specify the execution platform and device using the following options:

- **-p x -d y:** These two options are used together to select the desired device. The **-p** option specifies the platform ID, while **-d** specifies the device ID within that platform. The command `clinfo` can be used to obtain the corresponding IDs.
- **-t n:** Allows the user to select the device type (CPU, GPU, MIC, or FPGA) using a numerical value. If no platform is specified (**-p**), the benchmarks will run on the system’s default OpenCL platform.

By default, if no device is specified, the system executes the benchmarks on the CPU of platform #0. Adjustments were also made to scan all available

(a) Average execution time, Test input set.

(b) Average execution time, Train input set.

(c) Average execution time, Reference input set.

Fig. 1: Average execution times for each input set.

platforms for an OpenCL-compatible CPU, simplifying execution in complex configurations.

We have also implemented input file generators for various benchmarks, following the strategy originally used for CRC and CSR. These generators enable users to generate larger input files for further testing. Some examples include:

- `createswat_query` and `createswat_sampledb`: Generate DNA sequences based on Erwin Chargaff’s composition rules, necessary for the SWAT benchmark [10].
- `createbfs`: Generates input files for the BFS benchmark. This generator was manually developed by replicating the original files included in the suite, with a similar generator also added from the Rodinia benchmark suite [4].
- `createlud`: Creates matrices with valid LU decompositions for the LUD benchmark, ensuring the generated matrices are valid. OpenMP was incorporated to parallelize the creation of large matrices.

Additionally, options were added to customize the `LocalSize` parameter in various benchmarks, enhancing flexibility for execution in heterogeneous systems. These improvements ensured that OpenDwarfs benchmarks are easier to use and configure, providing a more uniform interface and enabling more precise and reproducible experiments across multiple platforms.

4 Experimental Results

This section presents the results obtained from experiments conducted using the different input sets developed for the OpenDwarfs suite. The experiments were performed on various hardware platforms to evaluate the performance of the benchmarks on heterogeneous architectures (CPU and GPU). The experiments, platforms, and results are described below.

The tests were conducted on the Gorgon cluster, configured with $2 \times$ AMD EPYC 7713 processors, each with 64 physical cores and 128 threads, providing a total of 128 cores and 256 threads; $2 \times$ Nvidia RTX 4500 GPUs; $1 \times$ Nvidia A100 GPU; $1 \times$ AMD W7800 GPU; and 1 TB of RAM. This system was used to execute all benchmarks on CPUs and GPUs, using different input sets (Test, Train, and Reference) for the experiments. Each of these categories simulates varying workloads: light, moderate, and heavy, respectively.

The execution times of the benchmarks were calculated as the average of 30 repetitions for each input set. This approach minimized noise in the results and provided more representative measurements. Approximately 6,300 executions were performed in total, translating to roughly 50 hours of experimentation.

Figures 1a, 1b, and 1c present the average times obtained for each benchmark, organized by input set and type of architecture (CPU and GPU). In the graphs, the Y-axis represents execution times in seconds, while the X-axis identifies the different benchmarks.

In addition to execution times, the speedup of GPU executions compared to CPU executions was calculated. Speedup reflects the performance ratio between

heterogeneous architectures, clearly showing the improvements achieved with GPUs. The speedups for the three input sets are shown in Figures 2a, 2b, and 2c. An additional metric called *GeoMean Speedup* (geometric mean speedup) was included, reflecting the geometric mean of the speedups obtained for each benchmark. This provides a more global view of performance.

Additional experiments were conducted to study the scalability of the benchmarks using only the Train input set while varying the number of threads on the CPU (1, 32, 64, 128, and 256 threads). Results indicate that most benchmarks fall short of ideal scalability, with speedups significantly lower than expected in most cases. An exception was the NQUEENS benchmark, which achieved a speedup of up to $\times 128$ when using 256 threads. For some benchmarks, such as BWA HMM and CSR, increasing the number of threads resulted in longer execution times. This could be due to code optimization issues or memory access contention. More detailed profiling analyses are suggested to determine the exact cause of these behaviors.

4.1 Conclusions from the Experiments

Based on the results, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- In general, GPU executions are faster than CPU executions. However, in many cases, the difference is not significant, likely because the CPU versions of the benchmarks are not sequential but instead leverage all available threads on the CPU.
- The variation in speedups increases with the size of the problems being solved. This suggests that GPUs are more effective for larger, more parallelizable tasks.
- Some benchmarks exhibit anomalies in their speedups, such as CSR and BWA HMM, which showed longer execution times with increased threads. This may be due to load imbalances, overhead in thread creation, or memory contention issues.

The experimental results demonstrate that OpenDwarfs is a valuable tool for evaluating performance on heterogeneous platforms. Although GPUs generally provide better execution times, exceptions and anomalies were found in some benchmarks. The scalability experiments revealed that few benchmarks scale optimally with the number of CPU threads, suggesting areas for improvement in the implementation of specific algorithms.

5 Future Work

Despite the advancements achieved, several tasks remain that could significantly improve the functionality and usability of the OpenDwarfs suite. The roadmap of the future work includes the following:

(a) Speedup for the Test input set.

(b) Speedup for the Train input set.

(c) Speedup for the Reference input set.

Fig. 2: Speedup for each input set.

- **Modifying Execution Resource Allocation:** Currently, it is not straightforward to modify the amount of hardware resources allocated to the benchmarks. It would be beneficial to allow users to select the amount of hardware resources they wish to use, which could be achieved by enabling modifications to the `LocalWorkSize` parameter in OpenCL. This would increase the suite’s flexibility, enabling more detailed evaluations.
- **Compatibility with current FPGA Systems:** Although the suite was originally designed to be compatible with Altera FPGAs, recent modifications have not been tested for this compatibility. It is recommended to conduct tests on various FPGA platforms to ensure that the suite remains compatible with this type of device and continues to fulfill its purpose of evaluating heterogeneous environments.
- **Expanding Available Input Sets:** While new file generators have been created for some benchmarks, several others lack adequate input sets. Future work should focus on providing file generators for all benchmarks that require them and reviewing the already incorporated generators to ensure they function correctly.
- **Addressing Anomalous Behaviors:** Certain benchmarks exhibited incorrect behaviors, such as the NEEDLE benchmark, which fails when processing large inputs. These issues should be investigated and resolved in future versions to ensure that all benchmarks can handle a broader range of inputs.
- **Porting to SYCL:** A natural next step is to provide a SYCL-based port of OpenDwarfs alongside our existing OpenCL implementation. SYCL, as a modern, single-source C++ abstraction over heterogeneous hardware, has seen growing adoption through Intel’s oneAPI, Codeplay’s ComputeCpp, and other open-source runtimes. By re-implementing each benchmark in SYCL, we would not only future-proof the suite against the gradual decline in pure OpenCL usage but also enable tighter integration with mainstream C++ toolchains, richer metaprogramming, and improved maintainability. We plan to investigate how to establish a dual-build workflow, allowing users to target either OpenCL or SYCL environments seamlessly in forthcoming releases.

6 Conclusions

OpenDwarfs 2025 delivers a thoroughly reengineered and modernized benchmark suite that resolves compatibility issues with contemporary OpenCL toolchains, incorporates automated input generators for key workloads, and provides comprehensive documentation to guide users through the build, execution, and analysis processes. Our extensive experimental evaluation on heterogeneous architectures demonstrates improved portability, scalability, and performance insights, while the enriched codebase and workflows ensure reproducibility. Together, these advancements establish OpenDwarfs 2025 as a robust, user-friendly framework for high-performance computing environments.

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References

1. Standard performance evaluation corporation, www.spec.org/benchmarks.html
2. Asanović, K., Bodik, R., et al.: The landscape of parallel computing research: A view from Berkeley. Tech. Rep. UCB/EECS-2006-183, EECS Department, University of California, Berkeley (12 2006)
3. Bartels, R.H., Golub, G.H.: The simplex method of linear programming using LU decomposition. *Communications of the ACM* **12**(5), 266–268 (1969)
4. Che, S., Boyer, M., et al.: Rodinia: A benchmark suite for heterogeneous computing. In: *IEEE Intl. Symp. on Workload Characterization (IISWC)*. p. 44–54. IEEE Computer Society, USA (2009)
5. Cooley, J.W., Lewis, P.A., Welch, P.D.: The fast Fourier transform and its applications. *IEEE Transactions on Education* **12**(1), 27–34 (1969)
6. Corrigan, A., Camelli, F., Lohner, R., Wallin, J.: Running unstructured grid based CFD solvers on modern graphics hardware. *Intl. J. for Numerical Methods in Fluids* **66**, 221 – 229 (05 2011)
7. Feldmeier, D.C.: Fast software implementation of error detection codes. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking* **3**(6), 640–651 (1995)
8. Feng, W.c., Lin, H., et al.: OpenCL and the 13 Dwarfs: A work in progress. In: *ACM/SPEC Intl. Conf. on Performance Engineering (ICPE)*. p. 291–294. ACM, New York, USA (2012)
9. Harish, P., Narayanan, P.J.: Accelerating large graph algorithms on the GPU using CUDA. In: *Intl. Conf. on High Performance Computing (HiPC)*. p. 197–208 (2007)
10. Kresge, N., Simoni, R.D., Hill, R.L.: Chargaff’s rules: The work of Erwin Chargaff. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* **280**(24), 172–174 (2005)
11. Krommydas, K., Feng, W., et al.: On the characterization of OpenCL Dwarfs on fixed and reconfigurable platforms. In: *IEEE Intl. Conf. on Application-Specific Systems, Architectures and Processors (ASAP)*. pp. 153–160 (06 2014)
12. Likas, A., Vlassis, N., Verbeek, J.J.: The global K-means clustering algorithm. *Pattern recognition* **36**(2), 451–461 (2003)
13. Yu, Y., Acton, S.: Speckle reducing anisotropic diffusion. *IEEE Trans. on Image Processing* **11**, 1260–70 (02 2002)